

PAPER • OPEN ACCESS

Effect of Throat Size on Performance of Microbubble Generator and Waste Water Treatment

To cite this article: Xayalak Vilaida *et al* 2019 *IOP Conf. Ser.: Mater. Sci. Eng.* **639** 012031

View the [article online](#) for updates and enhancements.

You may also like

- [Microbubble generation by microplasma in water](#)
Peng Xiao and David Staack
- [Binding dynamics of targeted microbubbles in response to modulated acoustic radiation force](#)
Shiying Wang, John A Hossack, Alexander L Klibanov *et al.*
- [Passive acoustic mapping of magnetic microbubbles for cavitation enhancement and localization](#)
Calum Crane, Marie de Saint Victor, Joshua Owen *et al.*

UNITED THROUGH SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY

 The Electrochemical Society
Advancing solid state & electrochemical science & technology

**248th
ECS Meeting**
Chicago, IL
October 12-16, 2025
Hilton Chicago

**Science +
Technology +
YOU!**

**Register by
September 22
to save \$\$**

REGISTER NOW

The advertisement features a central image of a smiling woman with long dark hair, wearing a brown blazer, standing against a blue background with a network of white dots and lines. The text is arranged in a clean, modern layout with a blue and white color scheme.

Effect of Throat Size on Performance of Microbubble Generator and Waste Water Treatment

Xayalak Vilaida¹, Sengratry Kythavone¹ and Toshio Iijima²

¹Department of Mechanical Engineering, National University of Laos, Vientiane, Laos

²Professor emeritus, Tokai University, Kanagawa, Japan

E-mail: x.vilaida@nuol.edu.la

Abstract. Microbubble can be widely applied to many fields such as waste water treatment from community, industry and agricultural. This study focus on set up experimental apparatus of microbubble generation to examine the optimum ratio between air to water for generating the best microbubble by using three different sizes of venturi with throat diameters of 3mm, 4mm and 5mm, respectively; and also for apply microbubble to treat community waste water. The venturi with throat diameter of 3mm can generate more microbubble than the other. When applied microbubbles to treat the sampling of the waste water, chemical oxygen demand (COD) of waste water was considered.

1. Introduction

Microbubbles are bubble smaller than one millimetre in diameter, but larger than one micrometre. A microbubble is smaller than a human hair (70 micrometres). They have widespread application in industry, life science, agriculture, and medicine. The composition of the bubble shell and filling material determines important design features such as buoyancy, crush strength, thermal conductivity and acoustic properties [1, 2, 3, 4].

Microbubbles actually may be used for drug delivery, biofilm removal, membrane cleaning, biofilm control and waste water treatment purposes. When pressured water is introduced into the generator, the velocity around the spherical body becomes extremely high compared to that at a generator exits; thus from the energy conversion principle the pressure a little downstream of the body becomes negative. With the aid of the negative pressure, air is automatically sucked through to small hole drilled around the pipe wall, and the air sucked is broken into a huge number of microbubbles by high shear introduced by water flow around the body. Thus, the microbubble generator can discharge a water jet with microbubble form the nozzle exit [5, 6, 7, 8].

The purpose of this research are to present and validate a physical model to predict the microbubble generator performance such as air to water suction rate and testing microbubble to waste water treatment form community.

2. Experimental apparatus and experimental procedure

2.1 Experimental Apparatus

Figure 1 shows the experimental apparatus that composes of following parts, 1; main water tank, 2; circulation water tank, 3; water pump, 4; venturi (main microbubble generator), 5; water regulation valve, 6; water flow meter of floater type, 7; air flow meter of floater type, 8; pressure gage, 9; electric circuit breaker, 10; vacuum gage, 11; bypass valve, 12; air regulating valve, 13; over flow pipe. The capacity of main water tank and circular water tank are 45 liters. Centrifugal pump power is 0.37kW with maximum pressure of 2 bar and maximum flow rate is 40

l/min. Venturi was placed at H= 0.15 m for all size of venturis. Figure 2 shows venturi with three different diameter d.

Figure 1 Experimental apparatus

Figure 2 Venturi with three different diameter d

Table 1 Specifications of venturi

Total length A (mm)	Outside dia. B (mm)	Air Section dia. C (mm)	Throat dia. d (mm)	Water inlet dia. D (mm)	Air suction pos. E (mm)
100	30	12	3	12	52
100	30	12	4	13	52
100	30	12	5	14	52

2.2 Experimental Procedure

In the present research work, experimental was conducted in the fish aquarium with maximum depth of 0.65 m. The venturi was placed at 0.15m for all size. At each venturi, water was discharge from a centrifugal pump at 9 -20 l/min. Three different sizes of venturi were designed with throat diameter of 3mm, 4mm, and 5mm respectively. Two flow meters are installed for both water and air flow measurements with pipe fitting system.

The microbubble generator test and their specification are shown in Figure 2 and Table 1. The three microbubble generators had the same total length, outside diameter, suction air diameter and air suction position, but different air throat diameter namely d=3mm, 4mm and 5mm are used.

3. Results and discussions

Table 2 shows the measurement result of mass of air in water. The two venturis with 3 mm of throat’s diameter is applying to water. The result was tested after 1 hour and 2 hours with varying water flow rate (9l/min – 16 l/min) and air suction rate (1.35 l/min – 4 l/min). Figure 3 shows the measurement result by using pure water. The two venturis with 3 mm, 4mm and 5mm of throat diameter were applying to water. The result was measured after 1 hour and 2 hours with varying water flow rate (9l/min – 16 l/min) and air suction rate (1.35 l/min – 4 l/min). Hence, the 15% of air to water ratio can generate up to 13.735 mg/l for two hours. The mass of air in water decreases when air to water ratio increase to 25% and it can generate around 2.773 mg/l.

Table 2 Mass of air in water

T (h)	Q _w (l/m)	Q _a (l/m)	Q _a /Q _w	M _w (mg)	M _a (mg)	M _a /M _w (mg/l)
				9.8432 ^a	0	0
1	9	1.35	0.15	9.7884	0.0548	5.567
2	9	1.35	0.15	9.7080	0.1352	13.735
1	12	2.4	0.20	9.8099	0.0333	3.381
2	12	2.4	0.20	9.7845	0.0587	5.964
1	16	4	0.25	9.8159	0.0273	2.773
2	16	4	0.25	9.7762	0.0670	6.807

^aRaw sample

The result of application via applying four microbubble generators for treatment of waste water from community. The sample was measured in every hour. Figure 3 compares mass of air in water for the air to water ratio 15%, 20% and 25%, respectively. The mass of air in water increase with time series. The air to water ratio 15% shows best result. The mass of air was increased from 10.311 mg/l after one hour and it reach up to 22.852 mg/l after six hours. It means the quality of waste water is improved. The quality of waste water that 25% of air to water ratio is lower than 20% of air to water ratio. The mass of air is increased form 4.575 mg/l after one hour and it reach up to 20.027 mg/l after six hours.

The application of venturi for 3 mm of throat diameter were shown in the figure 5. Community waste water was used as substances and the experiment was used 4 venturi together for 15% of air to water ratio. The result shown that the colour of waste water was changed from black to clay colour after 2 hours. It means oxygen in waste water increase whereas chemical oxygen demand (COD) reduce. In addition, the quality of waste water was improved steadily with time series. The experimental of treated waste water operates up to six hours.

4. Conclusions

From the Figure 3 and Figure 4 all size of throat diameter of venturi for air to water ratio of 15% can generate more microbubbles, and throat diameter of venturi with 3mm can generate more microbubble compare with other ones. For 2 hours of experiment the mass of microbubble or air in the water generated by venturi with throat diameter of 3mm, 4mm, and 5mm for air to water ratio of 15% are 0.1352mg (equivalent to 13.735mg/l), 0.0638mg (equivalent to 6.481mg/l), and 0.0236mg (equivalent to 2.397mg/l), respectively for volume of water 9.8432mg, therefore for applying microbubbles to treat the community waste water venturi with throat diameter of 3mm, and air to water ratio of 15% were used.

Figure 5 shows experimental result before and after treatment.

(A) Air to water ratio is 15%

(B) Air to water ratio is 20%

(C) Air to water ratio is 25%

Figure 3 Mass of air in water for each nozzle size and ratio of air to water

When applied microbubbles to treatment of the community waste water, COD of waste water significantly reduces. The venturi with throat diameter of 3 mm is applied to generate microbubbles with air to water ratio of 15%, 20%, and 25%, respectively and COD of waste water can be reduced by 55%, 43.5%, and 29.5% for air to water ratio as mentioned above.

5. References

- [1] Serizawa A. Flow characteristics and application of microbubble containing bubble two-phase flow, Proc. Of the 16 int. Congress of Chem. And Process Eng. – Prague, Czech. 2004.
- [2] Eriksson, J.C. and Ljunggren S., 1999, On the Mechanically Unstable Free Energy Minimum of a Gas Bubble which is Submerged in Water and Adheres to a Hydrophobic Wall, Colloid and Surface A: Physicochemical and Engineering Aspects, 159: 159–163J. Clerk Maxwell, A Treatise on Electricity and Magnetism, 3rd ed., vol. 2. Oxford: Clarendon, 1892, pp.68–73.
- [3] Kimura, T. and Ando, T., 2002, Physical Control of Chemical Reaction by Ultrasonic Waves, Ultrasonic Technology, 14: 7–8.
- [4] Kobayashi, F., Ikeura, H., Tamaki, M. and Hayata, Y., 2009a, Application of CO Micro- and Nano-Bubbles at Lower Pressure and Room Temperature to Inactivate Microorganisms in Cut Wakegi (*Allium wakegi* Araki), Acta Horticultrae, 875: 417-424.
- [5] Kobayashi, F., Hayata, Y., Ikeura, Y., Tamaki, M., Muto, N. and Osajima, Y., 2009b, Inactivation of Escherichia coli by CO Microbubbles at a Lower Pressure and Near Room Temperature, American Society of Agricultural Engineers, 52: 1621-1626.
- [6] Y. Yorozu, M. Hirano, K. Oka, and Y. Tagawa, “Electron spectroscopy studies on magneto-optical media and plastic substrate interface,” IEEE Transl. J. Magn. Japan, vol. 2, pp. 740–741, August 1987 [Digests 9th Annual Conf. Magnetics Japan, p. 301, 1982].
- [7] Pengphol S., J. Uthaiutra, O.A. Arqueron, N. Nomura and K. Whangchai. 2012. Reduction of residual chlopyrifos on harvested bird chilies (*Capsicum frutescens* Linn.) using ultrasonication and ozonation. Thai Journal Agricultural Science 44(5): 182-187.M. Young, The Technical Writer’s Handbook. Mill Valley, CA: University Science, 1989.
- [8] Zhang, H., L. Duan and D. Zhang, 2006. Absorbion kinetics of ozone in water with ultrasonic radiation. Ultrasonics Sonochemistry 14: 552-556.

Acknowledgement

We sinrely thank to Daido Kogyo Cooperation, Japan and Professor Dr. Katsumi Aoki of Tokai University for giving us very important information microbubble generation experiment setup.

Figure 4 Mass of air in water with 3mm throat diameter

(A) Waste water

(B) Treated wast water

Figure 5 Waste water treatment by using 4 venturis of 3 mm throat diameter